

Overview of Modern Software Platforms for Pharmaceutical Industry Management

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ABSTRACT

The digital evolution brings dynamic changes in pharmaceutical industries management. Introduction of IoT and AI turned industrial machines to smart systems. The integration of manufacturing, research labs and supply chains become more flexible with effective management. Modern software platforms supporting complex operations with cloud computing, AI, big data analytics and ERP systems. In this paper a brief survey conducted over available pharmaceutical software tools. The study highlights these tools role in enhancing product quality, operational maintenance, regulatory compliance, supply chain management over pharmacovigilance systems. The Block chain support in pharmacy industries secured data management and drug personalization. We covered some pharmaceutical regulation compliances worldwide for better healthcare systems for future societies.

Keywords: AI, Block Chain, ERP. Supply chain, drug discovery.

INTRODUCTION

IT services transformed every sector in globe in which Pharmaceutical industries are one of the fast growing domains. The digital transformation adopted modern software platforms to assist pharmaceutical industries in drug development and discovery process. The digital technology changed the laboratories into highly interactive automated work stations for enhanced clinical trials, regulatory and quality management services. Software evolution extremely

improved the supply chain operation and production management transparency. Some of the tools like Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS), Electronic Documentation System (EDS), Quality Assurance System (QAS), Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) and Block Chain Networks (BCN) are remarkable transformers of pharmacy industry workflows. The table 1 shows the evolution of software in pharmaceutical industry for each decade progression.

Table 1: Evolution in Pharmaceutical Industries

Period	Technology	Management
1960 – 1970	Basic laboratory control units, stand alone systems, Account management.	Paper entries, ledger management, manual entries.
1970 – 1980	Data Entry Systems, Inventory Management using DBMS, Accounting Systems.	Data Sharing and management using computers, Automation is budded.
1980 – 1990	Laboratory Information Systems, Electronic data managers, Statistical analysis software, Electronic Clinical Trail systems.	Reduced manual errorsFast lab schedules, Enhanced data storage and retrieval.
1990 - 2000	Business and Scientific logic integration, Enterprise Resource Planners (SAP/	Global Marketing, Regulatory authorities and compliances,

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	ORACLE), Supply Chain Management system, Advanced Clinical trial simulators, Electronic documentation systems.	Best manufacturing practices.
2000 – 2010	Quality management & assessment tools, Compliance validation systems, Digital signatures and secured transactions, Customized audit trail systems	Improved traceability, Risk reduction and management, Fast audit computations.
2010 – 2020	Cloud Computing based clinical trial systems, Real-time collaborative IoT, Enhanced global sharing technology, Machine Learning based data analytics Big Data systems, Web technologies assisted marketing tools.	Drug target identification, Digital supply chain management, monitoring, Predictive analytics, Smart systems management.
2020 – Now	AI Drug discovery and manufacturing tools, Digital twin systems, Block chain networks, Digital marketing systems, Process active analyzers, Decision support systems, Data Virtualization tools.	Generative AI assistance, Block chain security, personalized drug manufacturing and marketing.

Pharma Industrial Software:

IT services transformed every sector in globe in which Pharmaceutical industries are one of the fast growing domains

Table 2: Pharmaceutical Industry Software

S/W Package	Services	Advantages	Limitations	Applications
Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS)	Data Sampling, data management	Accuracy, Precision, Workflow automation, traceability.	High cost, Training.	Labs, research centers.
Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP)	Business operations, finance management integration.	Data centralization, efficient resource management.	Complex, expensive customization.	Business and Manufacturing automation.
Manufacturing Execution System (MES)	Process Monitoring & Control	Real-time traceability, error reduction.	Integration challenges	Improved production services
Clinical Trial Management System (CTMS)	Clinical trial services, documentation.	Patient tracking, regulatory compliances.	Large data set management distributed computing.	Labs, clinical research institutes.
Quality Management system (QMS)	Quality assurance, risk management, compliance governance.	Audit enhancement, compliance enforcement	Regular monitoring	QA departments in industries.

Figure 1: Yearly Maintenance Expenditure

Modern software tools in pharmacy industries inherited with manufacturing and regulatory compliance services. Balancing the company data access efficiency and security current software comes with following capabilities.

Regulatory Compliance:

The Food and Drug Regulation Authority internationally standardized some compliances considering the benefits of both industry and customers. The built-in framework for FDA in modern software provides basic to premium services like genealogy, material study, distributed certificates, electronic registrations and global authenticated compliance adoption.

Quality Assessment and Control:

Supporting drug mixing formulae analysis and potential calculations to estimate the patient centric drug development. Some of the major services like yield analysis, process flow testing, certificate analysis, clinical trials quality assurance. The QA service assists to deliver premium brand pharmaceutical products in long run.

Decision Support:

Integrates IoT with streamlined data centers. Provides real-time data alerts and threat detection in process stages. AI-driven support for manufacturing defect

detection. Drug discovery and prescription recommendations.

Supply Chain Optimization:

Tracking of products with demand forecasting service. Product date lookup, global marketing strategies, resource mapping, international market assessment and integration.

Advanced Analytics:

The modern digital-twin systems offering seamless predictive analytics with AI and ML techniques. The manufacturing pipeline analysis for better optimization in production. Various embedded systems are collaborated in delivering knowledge patterns to management.

Figure 1 provides the view of maintenance cost on software maintenance and operations by Indian top pharmaceutical industries.

Pharma Industrial SDLC:

Software Development Life Cycle involves series of pipelined process stages to develop effective software platforms to assist modern pharmaceutical industries. Figure 2 shows the various stages of SDLC. In modern era agile software development playing a key role which can be adoptable to dynamic environments.

Figure 2: Pharmaceutical Industry SDLC

Requirement Analysis Phase:

In this phase major task is to analyze the business and R&D to identify functional and non-functional requirements. Infrastructure required for maintain good compliances, supply chains, production units, IoT governance, data storage and retrieval are identified for industry. The security policy and stake holder demands are also analyzed in this SDLC module.

Regulatory Authority Analysis:

The phase focuses over standardization and certification of various national and international compliances over pharmaceutical industry. Management services supporting digital signatures, smart contracts under the guidelines of HIPPA/GDPA/FDA developed in this SDLC phase.

Technology Analysis:

The software platforms and necessary tools to support infrastructure of smart pharmaceutical industrial environments are identified. The best practices applied to choose software well suited for latest technologies and services to handle both production and marketing effectively. The foundational software frameworks are identified.

Design Phase:

According to specified SRS all the functional software modules are developed with integrated IoT environments. Various communication frameworks and security frameworks are collaboratively designed for modern industrial support.

Integration Phase:

The integration phase integrates the software modules of drug manufacturing plant and establishes a distributed data storage and communication environment among IoT and AI systems. Coordination and secured information exchange services are established. The integration among various technologies like IoT, AI, wireless communication and Block Chains under the compliances done here.

Pharmacovigilance:

In industrial environments and R&D labs continuous real-time monitoring is mandatory for effective risk detection. Vigilance software are integrated in pharmaceutical industries to provide better surveillance among units of production. Also Dev-Ops is one modern software technology highly suitable for maintaining consistent systems in environments with greater computing abilities.

Testing Phase:

The testing phase is vital to SDLC follows various phases like unit testing, integration testing, system testing and acceptance testing. The errors in functional systems are rectified here.

Deployment Phase:

The installation and maintenance of software systems in industries with proper user assistance completes the goals of SDLC. The continuous monitoring and maintenance services tune up company environments up to date to meet current challenges of pharmaceutical business.

CONCLUSION:

In this paper the evolution of pharmaceutical industries towards smart industry technology discussed. Various popular pharmaceutical industry management software are highlighted with their application areas. The drug regulation authority and compliances role also pointed for authentic drug discovery and clinical trails. We focused over SDLC phases of pharmacy software towards modern AI and IoT enabled service structures. Research is going on for high end data privacy governance in this domain. The Blockchain technology is already playing a significant role in open networks security among pharmacy industries network. In future there need more research in the direction of Quantum computing integration with pharmaceutical industry frameworks to handle huge data collections with high scale computing abilities.

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